

The Variation of West Sulawesi Dialects Used in STAIN Majene

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Abstract:

Dialect is a substandard or basic standard of the dialect itself which is also often associated with language, especially the spoken language in certain region. The researchers were interested to observe how vary the dialects used. The purpose of this research was to find out dialects' variation used during teaching and learning process of Speaking class in STAIN Majene. STAIN Majene is the newest university located in Majene regency, West Sulawesi province in which it is not the capital of the province. Yet, STAIN Majene students were coming from many different places and backgrounds. The methods used in the research were spoken data recording, place and the spoken language observation at the university. The researchers found that Mandarese is still the dominant dialect used in STAIN Majene area due to the students and non-students such as lecturers are mostly originally come from Majene and Polewali Mandar regencies.

INTRODUCTION

Dialect, a variety of a language that signals where a person comes from. The notion is usually interpreted geographically (regional dialect), but it also has some application in relation to a person's social background (class dialect) or occupation (occupational dialect) (García and Sandhu, 2015). The word dialect comes from the Ancient Greek dialektos "discourse, language, dialect," which is derived from dialegesthai "to discourse, talk." A dialect is chiefly distinguished from other dialects of the same language by features of linguistic structure—i.e., grammar (specifically morphology and syntax) and vocabulary. Nevertheless, while dialects of the same language differ, they still possess a common core of features.

Dialect is one of aspect that counts to be researched. It is one of indications of a person's identity mark. It is valuable to find out the uniqueness or the changes of any dialect. Dialect is so relatable and depend to the users since it is a part of social interaction and it evolves becoming one nation or community identification marker. The researchers have done a little pre-observation that research on West Sulawesi dialect is more likely nowhere to be found. Therefore, the researchers feel motivated to conduct this research.

Some linguists include phonological features (such as vowels, consonants, and intonation) among the dimensions of dialect, the standard practice is to treat such features as

aspects of accent (Hamann and Schmitz, 2005). In the sound system of American English, for example, some speakers pronounce greasy with an “s” sound, while others pronounce it with a “z” sound. Accent differences of this kind are extremely important as regional and class indicators in every language. Their role is well recognized in Great Britain, for example, where the prestige accent, called Received Pronunciation, is used as an educated standard and differences in regional accent, both rural and urban, are frequent. There is far less accent variation in Canada, Australia and large parts of the United States.

Frequently, the label dialect, or dialectal, is attached to substandard speech, language usage that deviates from the accepted norm—e.g., the speech of many of the heroes of Mark Twain’s novels. On the other hand, the standard language can also be regarded as one of the dialects of a given language, though one that has attracted special prestige. In a historical sense, the term dialect is sometimes applied to a language considered as one of a group deriving from a common ancestor. There is often considerable difficulty in deciding whether two linguistic varieties are dialects of the same language or two separates but closely related languages; this is especially true in parts of the world where speech communities have been little studied. In these cases, especially, decisions regarding dialects versus languages must be to some extent arbitrary.

Normally, dialects of the same language are considered to be mutually intelligible, while different languages are not (Kanon, 2003). Intelligibility between dialects is, however, almost never absolutely complete. On the other hand, speakers of closely related languages can still communicate to a certain extent when each uses his own mother tongue. Thus, the criterion of intelligibility is quite relative. In more-developed societies the distinction between dialects and related languages is easier to make because of the existence of standard languages. Sometimes sociopolitical factors play a role in drawing the distinction between dialect and language. Linguistic varieties that are considered dialects in one set of historical circumstances may be considered languages in another. Before the ethnic conflicts in the Balkans in the 1990s, Serbo-Croatian was viewed by its speakers as a single language consisting of several dialects, spoken in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Croatia; afterward, local communities began to talk of Croatian and Serbian as distinct languages.

Among the synonyms for dialect, the word idiom refers to any kind of dialect, or even language, whereas patois, a term from French, denotes rural or provincial dialects, often with a deprecatory connotation. A similar term is vernacular, which refers to the common, everyday speech of the ordinary people of a region. An idiolect is the dialect of an individual person at one time (Edward, 1990). This term implies an awareness that no two persons speak in exactly the same way and that each person’s dialect is constantly undergoing change—e.g., by the introduction of newly acquired words. Most recent investigations emphasize the versatility of each person’s speech habits according to levels or styles of language usage.

Dialect is a linguistic system used by a society to differentiate it from other societies. The following are the boundaries of the dialect area, namely: Inquete in the process of collecting general written data, records of informants that function as specific oral data and comparison method on vocabulary as interdisciplinary with historical and comparative linguistics. While the characteristics of a dialect are: It is a set of different local speech forms

which have common characteristics and each more similar to each other compared to other speech forms of the language same. Dialect can be recognized by a speaker's phonemes, pronunciation, and traits such as nasality, loudness and tonality (Etman and Beex, 2015).

The term dialect comes from a dialectical word in Greek. In Indonesian it is an accent. The borrowed word accent comes is often associated with a person or group. However, dialects from Arabic, namely lughah, which means language denotation. Dialect is the accent of the language, a symbol and specialization of the main language.

Dialects do not have to take all the spoken forms of a language. In its development, then one of the dialects with a slightly higher position, could be accepted as the standard language by the whole region (Budiarsa, 2015). Dialect is a substandard or basic standard of a language. Dialects are often associated with a person or group. But dialects are also often associated with the language, especially the language of the actions in the region. Dialect is a language, lambing and specialty specification of the parent language. In addition, dialects are the license system used by a community to distinguish from other people.

While the traits of the dialect are : It is a different set of local forms of speech, each having a common characteristic and each more like the other forms of speech of the same language. A dialect should not take all forms of speech out of a language. The whole region then accepted one dialect, a slightly superior one. Dialect growth and development are determined by language factors and outside factors. Natural conditions, affecting people's movements, make it easier for them to communicate with both the outside and the surrounding world. Then there is the bridge where the cultural exchange occurred. It became one of the means of language exchange. There are different dialects of relationship and superior languages that take place during migration, invasion or colonization. Not to be forgotten is the role of neighboring dialects or languages in the process of coming into existence (Swastika et al., 2016).

A dialect is an accent or is commonly called an indigenous speaking style owned by a person. Let's say the Mandarese speakers have different dialects of the Bugis speakers. Dialects contrast with different languages, that is, languages that are differentiated according to context. The variations differ from one another, but they still show great linguistic similarities to be inappropriate. Nevertheless, differentiating between dialects and distinct languages is often set against the background of symbolic and sociopolitics, not linguistic. Dialect is also used to refer to languages that are not spoken in the form of writing. Usually they use dialects based on geography and social factors. If it is based solely on pronunciation, the correct term according to the linguistic terminology is accent and not dialect. Therefore, the researchers are focus on only dialects variation used by the students of STAIN Majene during speaking classes.

THEORETICAL SUPPORT

The origin of the short dialect Reporting from the official website of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia, the growth and development of the dialect is determined by linguistic factors and extraneous factors (Majinka, 2005). Natural conditions, affect the space for the population to move, both make it easier for residents to

communicate with the outside and around the world. Then there is a bridge to cultural exchange. This has become a means of language exchange. The occurrence of various dialects is the relationship and superiority of language that is carried over when there is a migration of population, invasion or occupation. What should not be overlooked is the role of dialects or neighboring languages in the process of a dialect. Also read: Who invented the Indonesian language? From these neighboring dialects and languages, enter the interpretation of vocabulary, structure and pronunciation.

Then, there are among the dialects that are appointed as the standard language. So the role of standard language should not be forgotten. Each dialect has differences, even though the language family is the same (Brith, 2011). Dialect at first can be differentiated by the prosody, tone and intonation (Shport and Herd, 2020). However, in studying dialects the researchers also familiar with what the researchers called as "Phonetic Differences". These differences are in the field of phonology. Yet, in dialects studies some linguists will elaborate the sounds produced of each word by not focusing on the differences of vocabulary used but rather the tone and the stress.

METHOD

The researchers did the research at STAIN Majene during speaking classes. The purpose of this research was to find out the dialects' variation used in STAIN Majene by recording and observing the way the students speak whilst they speak formal or formally in speaking classes. Since STAIN Majene students were coming from many different places and backgrounds, therefore, the researchers assumed that it presumably enriches the dialects spoken in the area.

The researchers did qualitative research by applying phenomenology approach. The researchers recorded the data, found out the people background at STAIN Majene. The researchers wrote down as they heard some people speak and recorded it to finally analyze the data that the researchers have gotten. Apparently, there are already some data related to the dialects used in West Sulawesi collected by a culture practitioner. These data were also used for comparison in this research.

After the data were already collected, the researchers analyzed the data by matching and mapping the recorded sound to the dialects criteria listed already by the researchers. Besides, the researchers which are also coming from different area and using different dialect doing the self-checked.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The people of West Sulawesi Province, which consist of various customs and cultures, have several regional languages that are used by the people. The local language appears and develops in the area according to the cultural customs of the people. Magi (2018) in the book elaborates several regional dialects in West Sulawesi Province as follows:

Baras Dialect

Baras Dialect is one of the regional dialect found in West Sulawesi Province. This regional dialect is spoken by the people living in Baras Village, Baras District, North Mamuju

Regency, West Sulawesi Province. The speech area of Baras dialect is bordered by the speaking area of the Balinese language (east of Baras Village), the Bugis dialect speech area (in the North, and the speaking area of Sarudu dialect (South Sebalah of Baras Village).

Benggaulu Dialect

This regional dialect is spoken by people living in Karossa Village, Karossa District, Mamuju Tengah Regency, West Sulawesi Province. The speech area of Benggaulu is bordered by the speech area of the Bugis dialect (east), the speech area of the Sarudu language (north), and the speech area of the Mamuju language (south).

Mamasa Dialect

This regional dialect is also the native language of West Sulawesi Province. This regional dialect is spoken by people in Tawalian, Bambang (Bambam), Messawa, Dakka, Tonyaman, Karataun, and Bonehau Villages, West Sulawesi Province. There are five dialects of the Mamasa dialect, namely the Bambang dialect (Bambam) which is spoken in Bambang Village, Bambang District, Mamasa Regency, the Messawa dialect which is spoken in Messawa Village, Messawa District, Mamasa Regency, the Dakka dialect which is spoken in Dakka Village, Tapango District, Regency Polewali Mandar, the Pattae dialect spoken in Tonyaman Village, Binuang District, Polewali Mandar Regency, and the Kalumpang dialect spoken in Karataun Village, Kalumpang District, Mamuju Regency; Bonehau Village, Bonehau District, Mamuju Regency.

Mamuju Dialect

The regional dialect in West Sulawesi Province, has an almost even distribution in all districts, starting from Polewali Mandar Regency, Mamuju Regency, to Mamasa Regency, West Sulawesi Province. There are about nine dialects in the Mamuju language, namely the Buku dialect spoken in Buku Village, Mapilli District, Polewali Mandar Regency, the Pulliwa dialect spoken in Pulliwa Village, Bulo District, Polewali Mandar Regency, the Taek dialect spoken in Amassangan Village, Binuang District, Polewali Regency Mandar, the Pannei dialect is spoken in Tapango Village, Tapango District, Polewali Mandar Regency, the Aralle Tabulahan dialect is spoken in Aralle Village, Aralle Utara Village, and Aralle Selatan, Aralle District; Tabulahan Village, Tabulahan District, Mamasa Regency, the Campalagian dialect is spoken in Ongko Village, Campalagian District, Polewali Mandar Regency, the Tapalang dialect is spoken in Orobatu Village, Tapalang District, Mamuju Regency, the Binanga dialect is spoken in Binanga Village, Mamuju District, Mamuju Regency, and The Sinyonyoi dialect is spoken in Sinyonyoi Village, Kalukku District, Mamuju Regency.

Mandar Dialect

This regional dialect is spoken by the community in Napo Village, Limboro District, Polewali Mandar Regency, West Sulawesi Province. In addition, Mandar is also found in several villages in Majene Regency, such as in Labuang Village, East Banggae District; Adolang Village, Pamboang District; Mosso Village, Sendana District; Ulidang Village, Tammerodo Sendana District; Mekkatta Village, Malunda District; and Ulumanda Village, Ulumanda District. Mandar dialect has several dialects, including Balanipa dialect Pamboang,

Sendana, Ulu Manda 'and Awo' Sumakuyu. However, nowadays it is difficult to distinguish between one dialect and another. Actually, West Sulawesi Province has many regional languages. However, Mandar is the dominant dialect used by the people of the province. The Mandar dialect comes from the Malay Polynesian family. There is no clear explanation since when the use of the Mandar dialect in the daily life of the Mandar people. There is an opinion that the Mandar language was used at the same time as the emergence of the first humans in Mandar land.

The accent in West Sulawesi varies from region to region. The researchers focused on the students as the language users at STAIN Majene. To be exact, there are 2337 students of STAIN Majene coming from many backgrounds and places. But, based on the students' data archived at STAIN Majene that students of the university are dominated by Polewali Mandar and Majene regencies' background.

As we know, Mandarese is the native language of Polewali Mandar, the people are very thick with the language. Polewali Mandar is very close to Majene. The use of Mandarese is very often found in the daily activities of the speakers. However, their language delivery varies considerably due to different dialect factors, for example different intonations of voice and tone of voice between rural or mountainous and coastal communities. Between the mountainous and coastal communities have one common language, namely the Mandar dialect. However, their accents have almost nothing in common due to various factors, for example the mother tongue they learned from a long time ago has been contaminated with the language made up by their ancestors.

Therefore, when conveying messages to other people, it will sound a little off the mark from the normal standard Mandarese. In the Mandarese itself, there are many words adopted from Indonesian which are difficult to interpret in Mandar. Finally, when talking about these words, the Mandar people pronounce them in Indonesian. For example, "Glasses". There is no specific word of the word in the Mandarese. Same goes for milk, nest (bird's nest), flowers, etc. In West Sulawesi, most of the people work as farmers and fishermen. Because the location of this area is mostly between mountains and oceans in which STAIN Majene also located in such area.

The normal Mandarese sounds like usual, just like the Indonesian accent in general. However, when we heard the mountain people speak, the Mandar dialect was slightly overstated and had a soft tone and sounded weak. Generally, hill people speak in a slightly suppressed voice at the end of their speech. Meanwhile, coastal people are generally inversely related to hill people. You could say their voices sounded more powerful and had high tones when speaking. According to the information the researchers got, this was triggered by the sound of the waves on the beach. So, when communicating with each other, you must use a slightly loud voice and volume so that it reaches the listener's ears properly (Uswatunnisa, 2016).

Mandar dialect has several dialects, including Balanipa dialect Pamboang, Sendana, Ulu Manda 'and Awo' Sumakuyu. However, nowadays it is difficult to distinguish between one dialect and another. Mandar dialect has a percentage difference of about 81% -100% from other languages in West Sulawesi Province. Actually, West Sulawesi Province has many

regional languages. However, Mandar is the dominant dialect used by the people, especially the students of STAIN Majene. The Mandar dialect comes from the Malay Polynesian family. There is no clear explanation since when the citizens use Mandar dialect in the daily life. There is an opinion that the Mandar language was used at the same time as the emergence of the first humans in Mandar land.

These factors do not stand alone, but complement each other. Dialects can be classified into two types, namely: Dialect 1 is due to the natural conditions around which the dialect is used throughout its development. Dialect is produced because of two complementary factors, namely time and place. For example, the Malay language used in the Manado area is the Manado language which is historically spoken in the Manado area. Dialect 2 is the language spoken outside the area of use. The relationship with the Indonesian language, for example, the Indonesian language used in the Bali area, Bugis and Sundanese which are spoken by people who come from these tribes are dialects 2.

However, the Indonesian language used in Ambon, Manado, and Jakarta is not included in dialect 2 because it is considered as a region where the Indonesian language is spoken. Social dialect The variety of languages used by certain groups. So it is easy to distinguish other groups of people. This group consists of groups of occupation, age, activity, gender, education, and so on. The various social dialects show special features known as argot and slang. Until the end of the 19th century, argot was still defined as the special language of adventurers, thieves and beggars.

CONCLUSION

The researchers have found that until early 2021, Mandarese are still the major dialect used by the students of STAIN Majene because most of them are from Majene and Polewali Mandar area. Other dialects that are used by the students are Mamuju, Beggaulu and Baras. There is also Javanese dialect because students who come from Wonomulyo area are tend to practice the dialect. We should learn about the different dialects found in West Sulawesi, as well as their names, as they are all very closely related. Dialect will have distinct characteristics in each area of West Sulawesi, as previously detailed in this research. Furthermore, not only are the characteristics different in each region, but there are also many terms that vary even though they have the same meaning in each region, which is the foundation for dialect variations in West Sulawesi. Natural conditions influence the amount of space available for the population to move, making it easier for residents to communicate with the outside world. Then there's a cultural exchange bridge. This has evolved into a method of language exchange. The presence of various dialects reflects the relationship and superiority of language that is carried over when there is population migration, invasion, or occupation. The role of dialects or neighboring languages in the dialect process should not be overlooked.

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